

Fermat's Principle, Optical Lagrangian, Hypothetical Velocity and the Moving Mirror

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In (1) Fermat's least time principle is applied to the case of light reflecting from a mirror moving at a constant velocity. In (2),(3) we argued that one could bypass the minimization process by introducing a conserved hypothetical velocity along the mirror interface which represents a hypotenuse such that the relative velocities along the rays (incident and reflected) were $\cos(90-A)$ and $\cos(90-B)$ projections with A and B being the incident and reflected angles. Then $H \sin(A) = v\text{-relative}(A)$ and $H \sin(B) = v\text{-relative}(B)$.

In this note we consider the theory of optical Lagrangians/Hamiltonians (4) in which optical momentum is represented by a unit vector in the direction of motion multiplied by the index of refraction n. (Physical momentum is vacuum momentum multiplied by this value.)

Optical momentum may be broken into 3 space components with the z axis being treated as an independent parameter. Optical Hamilton's equations $dH/dx_k = dp_k/x^3 = 0$ lead (for refraction for example) to optical $p_x = n_1 \sin(A) = n_2 \sin(B)$ or Snell's law.

We argue that n is linked to the speed of light through c/n . For the case of a moving mirror, n is the same for incident and reflected rays, but the relative velocity is not. We argue that if n is thought of as $1/\text{relative velocity}$ then p optical becomes a unit vector in the ray direction multiplied by $1/\text{relative velocity}$. This then leads to: $p_x \text{ optical} = \sin(A) / v\text{-relative}(A) = \sin(B) / v\text{-relative}(B)$ i.e. the same result as the hypothetical velocity approach (and ultimately Fermat's principle).

Fermat's Principle of Least Time

A moving mirror with a surface of length L in the x direction moving with speed v in the negative y direction may have incident light hit at a point x on the surface making an angle A with the normal. It then reflects with angle B (from the normal i.e. y axis). Using $da = c ta$ and $db = c tb$ one may find an expression for $ta+tb$ as a function of x as done in (1). Taking $d t \text{ total} / dx = 0$ leads to the fundamental result:

$$\sin(A) - \sin(B) = -v/c \sin(A+B) \quad ((1))$$

This may be rewritten in terms of relative velocities with v being projected along the incident and reflected rays i.e.

$$\sin(A)/v\text{-relative}(A) = \sin(B)/ v\text{-relative}(B) \quad ((2)) \quad (\text{see (2), (3)})$$

Hypothetical Velocity Approach

In (2) and (3) we argued that ((2)) is linked to the idea of a hypothetical velocity which is along the x-axis, but nevertheless acts as a hypotenuse with $v\text{-relative}(A)$ and $v\text{-relative}(B)$ being $\cos(90-A)$ and $\cos(90-B)$ projections. Then:

$$H \cos(90-A) = H \sin(A) = v\text{-relative}(A) \quad \text{and} \quad H \sin(B) = v\text{-relative}(B)S \quad ((3))$$

This yields ((2)), but does not involve finding an expression for overall time, taking the derivative $d t_{\text{total}} / dx$ and setting it equal to 0.

Optical Lagrangians

In this note, we wish to show that the hypothetical velocity approach seems to be consistent with a generalized optical Lagrangians/Hamiltonian formalism if one considers n to be linked to light speed through c/n . In the case of relative velocities, n in the optical Lagrangian theory may be replaced by $1/ v\text{-relative}$, we suggest.

The optical Lagrangian theory (4) considers three spatial coordinates x_1, x_2, x_3 with x_3 being the independent variable (x_1 and x_2 depending on x_3). For a two dimensional problem (like reflection from a stationary mirror, refraction and reflection from a mirror moving at constant velocity) one may use x_1 and x_3 . In such a case optical Lagrangian theory gives an optical momentum of:

$$P_{\text{optical}} = n \text{ (index of refraction) } * \text{ unit vector in direction of light motion } ((4))$$

(One may note that multiplying p_{optical} by p_{vacuum} yields the physical momentum.)

$$\text{A Hamiltonian is given as: } H = - \sqrt{(n^2 - p_1^2)} \quad \text{where } p_1 = p_{x_{\text{optical}}} \quad ((5))$$

Hamilton's equation: $dH/dx_1 = dp_1/dt$ holds and given that no x_1 appears in ((5)) one has p_1 being constant. This implies conservation of both the optical momentum and physical momentum projection in the x direction i.e. along the surface of the mirror or interface of media.

For the problem of light reflecting from a mirror moving at constant velocity in the negative y direction, n is the same for the reflected and incident rays, but relative velocity is not.

We suggest modifying the optical Lagrangian/Hamiltonian theory in the following way. We suggest that n is linked to light speed through c/n . We identify n with $1/ v\text{-relative}$. In such a case, for the moving mirror problem:

$$P_{x_{\text{optical}}} = \sin(A) / v\text{-relative}(A) = \sin(B) / v\text{-relative}(B) \quad ((6))$$

This is the same as Fermat's principle and the hypothetical velocity result. Thus the hypothetical velocity approach seems to be equivalent to a generalization of the optical Lagrangian/Hamiltonian theory.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Fermat's least time principle requires finding an expression for the total time (traveled by incident and reflected/refracted rays) in terms of x and then taking the derivative with respect to x and setting it equal to 0. We suggested in (2) and (3) a simpler method of a hypothetical velocity H along the x axis which is conserved. This H acts as a hypotenuse for $\cos(90-A)$ and $\cos(90-B)$ projections which yield the relative velocities of the incident and reflected rays i.e. $H \sin(A) = v\text{-relative}(A)$ and $H \sin(B) = v\text{-relative}(B)$. This yields the same result as Fermat's principle. Here we argue that the hypothetical velocity approach is equivalent to a generalized optical Lagrangian/Hamiltonian theory. Such a theory defines optical momentum as n (index of refraction) times a unit vector in the direction of motion. Hamilton's equation indicates that p_x optical is constant i.e. $n_1 \sin(A) = n_2 \sin(B)$ for refraction. For reflection from a moving mirror $n_1 = n_2$, but we suggest the following generalization. We take n to be linked to light speed through c/n . Then we suggest that for the moving mirror problem n may be replaced by $1/v\text{-relative}$. This then leads to the hypothetical velocity result which in turn is equivalent to Fermat's minimal time principle.

References

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